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Publishable Executive Summary

PYSOLO (PYrolysis of biomass by concentrated SOLar pOwer) project brings together 9 partners from 4 EU countries with the aim of preparing the ground for a novel ground-breaking and fully renewable process combining concentrated solar power and biomass pyrolysis. Thanks to the use of solar heat in the pyrolysis process, the production of valuable products bio-oil, biochar and pyrogas can be maximized and the associated CO₂ emission minimized, with economic and environmental benefits compared to conventional pyrolysis. The proposed system uses particles heat carrier, ensuring operational flexibility and avoiding the need of heat transfer surface in the pyrolysis reactor that facilitates the system scale-up.

Specifically, PYSOLO process aims at developing at TRL4 the two key unit operations of this novel solar pyrolysis system, namely: (i) the solar particle receiver and (ii) the pyrolysis reactor with the associated particle-char separator.

The very innovative feature of PYSOLO lies in its innovative and unique coupling of pyrolysis technology with high temperature CSP system. This ground-breaking feature can potentially offer the following main advantages:

- delivering solar bio-oil, electricity or pyrogas and biochar for many energy and non-energy uses, when solar energy
- supplies the heat necessary for the pyrolysis process, either in sunny hours or by exploiting high temperature stored solids;
- run in self-mode the pyrolysis process (i.e. with electric heating or burning pyrogas and biochar), when solar energy is not sufficient and the TES unit is discharged;
- providing balancing services to the electric grid:
 1. from the conversion of the available pyrogas when solar energy or TES are sufficient to maintain the pyrolysis process running and the grid requires the generation of additional electric power;
 2. by using low-cost excess electricity from non-programmable RES (i.e. PV and wind) and converting it in high temperature thermal energy via the induction electric heating system.

The PYSOLO Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) offers a strategy to maximise the project impact by addressing relevant stakeholder and target groups via suitable channels and instruments. The plan describes online and offline activities and materials, defines strategic goals based on key performance indicators (KPIs) and risk assessment, and presents means of verification of the implemented activities and materials. It also presents the project's visual identity and describes relevant standards and procedures.

This document is the first version of D5.1 Dissemination and communication plan, which acts as a living document and will be updated yearly.

1. Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP)

1.1. Objectives

The key objectives of the PYSOLO CDP are i) raising EU-wide and global awareness of the availability of an efficient and environmentally friendly solar pyrolysis technology for biochar and bio-oil production and ii) increasing its acceptance. To achieve this goal, the communication and dissemination (C&D) strategy presented in this document will be implemented continuously during the entire project by all consortium members. In particular, in line with the concept of “Open Innovation” promoted by the EC, attention will be paid to the involvement of all key stakeholder groups in the project dissemination activities.

More in detail, the PYSOLO CDP aims at:

- Creating demand for the products and methodologies developed and evaluated in the project in the renewable technology areas.
- Creating awareness, acceptance and support in the society at large for new bio-based materials in relation to direct application of renewable energy sources.
- Creating market pull for project methods and products, such as bio-oil or biochar and cross-fertilisation.
- Publishing results in peer reviewed journals and at conferences to engage the wider scientific and industrial community.
- Establish proactive project communication and awareness approaches targeted towards students and the relevant segment of the society.

1.2. Definitions

Communication, dissemination and exploitation represent highly interlinked activities that support and complement each other in order to maximise the project impact. The three elements serve different purposes, address different stakeholder and target groups and thus require different instruments. The differences and purposes of these single elements are explained and defined in the following.

Communication activities serve the purpose to introduce the project to relevant stakeholder groups, the media as well as the broad public and inform about the project’s objectives, progress, results and related activities (e.g. workshops and other events). This is executed through strategic and targeted promotion and information measures addressing a multitude of audiences and conveying clear messages. Communication measures aim at creating interactive exchange between project partners, relevant stakeholders and the society by continuously ensuring and increasing stakeholder engagement and interest in project related issues. Hereby, stakeholder acceptance of the developed technologies and pyrolysis products and their application is increased. Effective communication is ensured through the choice of suitable communication channels (such as press releases, social media and digital networks, videos and the project website). Transparent and

continuous communication activities demonstrate how EU-funded projects contribute to tackle societal and environmental challenges, and that taxpayer money is spent consciously and in a beneficial way in order to develop and introduce impactful positive solutions.

Dissemination activities present an essential element of good research practice by circulating knowledge and making project results publicly available free of charge to any interested stakeholder group by following standards such as Open Access (OA) and the FAIR science approach. A focus is set on the scientific and academic community that can best make use of project results through subsequent research and application and adaptation of methods. The dissemination strategy therefore focuses on scientific OA publications in journals, as theses and in conference proceedings as well as the creation of and contribution to suitable OA databases. Furthermore, dissemination includes presentations at (scientific) conferences, workshops and science fairs. Additional media will increase the original focus-radius of the generated results and support the transfer and dissemination of generated knowledge into related but also other scientific disciplines. The overarching goal of all dissemination activities is to maximise the impact of generated results, support future research and make scientific results a common good.

Exploitation describes the process of making concrete use of generated results for scientific, commercial, societal and political purposes by identifying exploitable results and respective stakeholder groups. This includes stakeholder groups like researchers, policy makers, industrial bodies, SMEs, entrepreneurs, farmers, fertiliser manufacturers, etc.. The results can be exploited by application and transfer of results and technologies for scientific purposes, developing, creating and marketing a product, technology or process, by creating and providing a service, by standardisation of activities and by supporting the design of beneficial political frameworks and instruments. The project partners can exploit results themselves or facilitate exploitation through others, e.g. by making results available under open license agreements.

1.3. Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Tasks and Deliverables

The PYSOLO **WP5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation** includes the following tasks and deliverables, which will be executed throughout the project duration in order to maximise the project impact on a multi-perspective level.

Table 1: List of tasks within WP5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Task No.	Title	Lead	Date
T5,1	Dissemination and Communication plan	NOVA, EUCORE, All	M1-48
T5.2	External communication & dissemination	NOVA, POLIMI, All	M1-48
T5.3	Internal communication platform	NOVA	M1-48
T5.4	Exploitation, market analysis	NOVA	M1-48

Table 2: List of deliverables within WP5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

No.	Title	Lead	Form	Level	Due Date
D5.1	Dissemination and Communication plan	NOVA	Document, report	PU	M6
D5.2	Exploitation Plan	NOVA	Document, report	SEN	M9
D5.3	Dissemination and communication package WP5 – RP1	NOVA	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU	M18
D5.4	Dissemination and communication package WP5 – RP2	NOVA	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU	M36
D5.5	Dissemination and communication package WP5 – RP3	NOVA	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU	M48
D5.6	Market analysis and market entry strategy	NOVA	Document, report	PU	M48

1.4. C&D Timeline

Communication activities will take place continuously throughout the duration of the project and corresponding materials will be prepared. It is foreseen that communication efforts will increase in particular when a planned milestone (MS) is reached (i.e. when units are up and running: MS 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10), publications are published and to be disseminated, when events are planned that are to be advertised and celebrated, and at the successful project conclusion. Within the project (runtime: July 2023 to June 2027), the following milestones are foreseen as according to the grant agreement:

Figure 1: Timeline of PYSOLO (runtime 1st July 2023 to 30th June 2027) with the milestones (MS) at which units are up and running. Indicated is also the due date of the CDP which is the current point in time of the project.

All partners are encouraged to communicate the project’s key messages to the different types of stakeholders with targeted communication measures to position PYSOLO within the hot topics of sustainable energy, transition to a circular and fossil-free economy, CO₂-emission reduction, and biomass resource availability.

1.5. Stakeholder Analysis

C&D efforts address the following specific stakeholder groups through effective channels and instruments in English and/or the respective stakeholder language:

Table 3: Identified stakeholder groups, their specifics and the C&D goals per each group

Stakeholder Group	Specifics and C&D Goals
Academia and scientific societies and platforms	The scientific community, respective societies and platforms (IEA, IRENA etc.) that are active in the fields relevant with respect to PYSOLO findings will be the target of C&D efforts, e.g. through publication of scientific and technical papers.
Farmers & farmers associations	After positive experimental evaluation of biochar ¹ and the aqueous phase of bio-oil (produced by biomass pyrolysis) as fertilisers, PYSOLO aims at communicating them as a bio-based alternative to conventional fertilisers.
Industry & related communities	PYSOLO's goal is to make relevant industries and industrial communities in the fields of renewable energy and fuels, CSP technology and fertilisers as well as oil companies aware of the PYSOLO technologies and (new applications) of products. This way, they will gain a new potential technology e.g. to increase the fraction of bio-products in existing biorefineries.
Key associations	Different key associations across the value-chain (e.g. European Biomass Association, International DME Association, farmers associations, ESTELA, PROTERMOSOLAR, etc.) will be the target of C&D activities in order to create market pull for project methods and products such as bio-oil or biochar and cross-fertilisation.
Legislators, policy makers, etc.	The commercial deployment of PYSOLO technologies may be blocked if European regulations in the coming decades will not be effective in determining favourable market conditions. Therefore, PYSOLO will address

¹ Biochar meets specific requirements laid down in the EU Fertiliser Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2019/2009, EC marked fertilisers) as amended by Commission delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2088) as "CMC14" (Compound Material Category 14 "pyrolysis and gasification materials").

	<p>different legislators and policy makers with specific reference to environmental and energy authorities (such as the European Environmental Agency, European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency and the European Energy Agency). They will be informed about biomass selection for energy use and the environmental performance of the PYSOLO technologies in order to consider this in legislations on bio-energies. For this, policy-makers will be invited to participate in the PYSOLO stakeholder workshop/webinar.</p>
<p>Players of the bioenergy and biofuel sector</p>	<p>This stakeholder group will be addressed through concise C&D activities. They need to be gained as supporters and mediators for the successful deployment of PYSOLO's renewable energy technologies in order to decarbonise the transport sector and decarbonise and defossilise the chemical industry through CSP, biofuels and biobased products.</p>
<p>Regulatory organisations and local & regional authorities, NGOs. etc.</p>	<p>This stakeholder group will be addressed in order to gain insight to legal and institutional issues that have to be addressed when a biomass to liquid fuel plant is to be established.</p>
<p>Press & media, general public & EU citizens</p>	<p>Since the deployment of bioenergy and solar energy technologies may be blocked in some areas by NIMBY² opposition towards new chemical plants and land occupation, PYSOLO aims i) at increasing the awareness of the general public in the EU and abroad for environmental issues and for challenges that the industry is facing to become climate-neutral, ii) at increasing acceptance for developed solutions and technologies and iii) at displaying that tax-payer money is spent in a responsible, impactful and meaningful way.</p>

² NIMBY = “not in my backyard”, i.e. persons/residents that oppose developments and technologies only because they are in close proximity. They would potentially tolerate or support them if respective plants were built farther away.

1.6. Expected Impacts and Key Messages

The PYSOLO Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities are of the utmost importance to maximise the societal, scientific, environmental and economic/technological impacts of EU R&I funding.

Therefore, the PYSOLO C&D strategy addresses the following impact areas:

- **Economic/Technological:** PYSOLO aims at opening a new market for solar bio-oil, pyrogas and biochar for many energy and non-energy uses (for instance PYSOLO results could be used by industries requiring the heating of solids at high temperature or actors dealing with chemical recycling of plastics and other end-products via pyrolytic routes). Significant impacts are also expected on agriculture: Biochar, when added to soil, involves the co-benefit of increasing the fertility of the soil and therefore crop yields. Last but not least PYSOLO will substantially increase the competitiveness of the industries involved as PYSOLO partners and stakeholders. It will create new and strengthen established markets for bio-based feedstock and related products. These markets will support the European bioeconomy as well as its competitiveness and productivity.
- **Scientific:** Scientific impact will be generated by providing valuable results and knowledge in the field of renewable energy and applications of pyrolysis products (by following an Open Access and FAIR science approach). This will strengthen the positioning and scientific leadership of EU researchers in the field of CSP and pyrolysis technologies. Furthermore, PYSOLO aims at supporting and fostering young scientists by training PhD students and offering scientific workshops.
- **Environmental:** Positive environmental impacts will be ensured through solar powered process, sequestration of carbon through biomass use, enabling renewable energy scenarios through flexible provision of different products that can be used as energy carriers and potential substitution of conventional fertilisers or other feedstocks.
- **Societal:** By targeting the general public, press and media, PYSOLO aims at raising awareness towards climate and environmental issues and at increasing acceptance of sustainable innovative technological solutions. Societal impact will be achieved by PYSOLO as it results will contribute to: i) minimising of CO₂-emissions and waste by increased resource recovery, ii) creating new jobs in the energy sector, iii) increasing the competitiveness, independence and productivity of European circular economy, and iv) contributing to achieve Sustainable Development Goals (especially affordable and clean energy, industry, innovation and infrastructure, climate action and life on land). Furthermore, PYSOLO will ensure that taxpayer money is spent in a meaningful, beneficial and impactful way.

The CDP further aims to communicate the following identified core messages of each WP to targeted stakeholder groups:

Table 4: Key tasks and messages of each WP and targeted stakeholder groups

No.	Title	Key Tasks and Messages	Stakeholder Group
WP1	Project coordination and management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> establish an efficient management structure to monitor the overall project implementation; ensure early identification of problems and to enable timely contingency measures; monitor overall scientific quality, leading to the achievement of project objectives and to the formulation of high-quality deliverables and conclusions; ensure adequate communication flow among partners and with the EC; ensure efficient management of ethics issues. 	PYSOLO project partners, EC, tax payers
WP2	Development of the pyrolysis unit for solar pyrolysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> characterise the operations of the auger and FB pyrolysis reactors with different PHCs; validate at TRL 4 the pyrolysis processes in auger and FB reactors with selected PHC; erect, test and validate the induction heating of heat carrier particles in fluidised bed and auger reactor configurations; erect, test and validate the hot and cold PHC-char separation unit; perform modelling of the pyrolysis processes from the molecular to the reactor scale. 	Industry & related communities, players of the bioenergy and biofuel sector, related projects, academia
WP3	Development of the solar receiver for solar pyrolysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> characterise the PHCs to support the selection of the most promising for solar pyrolysis; design, build and test the solar receiver and the peripheral components with different types of heat carriers; develop a detailed thermal model for the receiver, to provide performance correlations to be used in the overall PYSOLO plant model and scale-up study. 	Industry & related communities, players of the bioenergy and biofuel sector, related projects, academia
WP4	Overall system analysis and scale-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> identify the target biomass for the PYSOLO process; provide input to technology developers in WP2-3 on the most promising PHC and on the experimental matrices, based on the complete process simulation study; calculate techno-economic KPIs of PYSOLO solar pyrolysis with process simulations and economic models and compare the results with benchmark systems; 	Industry, related communities, players of the bioenergy/biofuel sector, related projects, academia, farmers/farmer associations

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identify the risks and propose mitigation measures for a safe development and deployment of the PYSOLO processes; • assess the solar pyrolysis PYSOLO process with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA); • perform a pre-engineering scale-up study of commercial PYSOLO processes and of a pilot plant for technology demonstration at TRL6-7 in a follow-up project; • perform techno-economic analysis of the integration of the PYSOLO concept in three refineries in Southern Europe. 	
WP5	Communication, dissemination and exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • coordinate and to provide support for the dissemination of project results – internally as well as externally; • create “public relations” in terms of building up and maintaining contacts with target groups and key stakeholders with the intention of engaging stakeholders and the public in all core aspects of the project; • ensure efficient commercial exploitation of the project results; • achieve the highest possible benefit for scientists, policy makers, professionals and society by raising public awareness to the renewable energy sector and the new approaches funded by the EU; • manage IPR. 	All stakeholder groups including general public, press and media and policy makers for the C&D measures, and key industry associations for exploitation

2. Communication and Dissemination

2.1. Project Identity

2.1.1. Logo

In order to present PYSOLO in a modern, appealing and cohesive way and increase its recognition, the project received a modern and clear project identity. This identity is part of task T5.2 and is used for all internal and external C&D activities and materials. The project identity includes a project logo and related graphical identity, i.e., a specific colour code, templates for Microsoft PowerPoint and Microsoft Word for deliverables, reports and milestones, a website design, templates for non-scientific publications as well as material for online and offline communication such as (digital) banners, posters, infographics, brochures, flyers and factsheets. The created communication and dissemination material is going to be used at various occasions (e.g., conferences, fairs, science exhibitions) to communicate the project objectives and aspired benefits to various stakeholder groups and raise awareness for the challenges tackled within the PYSOLO project. These measures will increase stakeholder engagement and acceptance of developed technologies, products and applications, and their related industries.

The graphical identity was created with joint input from the entire project consortium. NOVA provided a first set of logo suggestions (based on an online survey via the tool Survey Monkey on colours, shapes/images and associations with the term “PYSOLO”) for which the consortium voted online. In the next step, design version 3 (Fig. 1) was modified and accepted as final logo (Fig. 2) during the face-to-face (F2F) meeting in Milan, Italy, in September 2023. The logo showcases a sun representing concentrated solar power (CSP), a brown striped circle segment standing for wood biomass and a blue circle segment with differently shaped squares delineating mirrors collecting and concentrating solar radiation.

Figure 2: Five different PYSOLO logo drafts and the result of the online voting to determine the preferred design version

Figure 3: Final PYSOLO logo

2.1.2. Templates

Following the logo design, a colour code was developed which can be found in the annex of this document. This colour code was used for the design of the Word and PowerPoint templates (Fig. 3) intended for reporting, deliverables, milestones and presentations. Furthermore, name tags to be used for PYSOLO events were designed using the PYSOLO colour code. These aim at increasing and supporting the external recognition of PYSOLO and ensure a cohesive project representation.

Figure 4: PYSOLO PowerPoint and Word (deliverable) templates and name tags

2.2. Internal Communication

Good internal communication aims at sharing information and data, supporting project management and strengthening the coherence between the different partners' specialisations to ensure the success of the project. Furthermore, it supports team spirit and ensures that each partner exploits its existing contacts with experts and decision/policymakers.

2.2.1. Internal Communication Platform

An internal communication platform was set up to simplify timely data exchange, provision of templates and information to partners and to offer a platform for direct communication. The internal platform is based on the Nextcloud system and was established by NOVA.

It offers different sub-menus:

- a dashboard/entry page that can be personalised by each member as according to their needs,
- a sub-menu for direct data/file upload and exchange (for general internal sharing; if necessary access can also be granted to external persons for specified files),
- a sub-menu for up and download of shared pictures,
- a sub-menu with the activity protocol of the platform,
- a contact sub-menu which can be used to contact the platform members via email either individually or as bulk (by establishing a specific member group),
- a calendar sub-menu which offers the possibility of inserting and managing both own personal dates and appointments (by creating a deck), and upcoming project and deliverable dates one is assigned to,
- a deck sub-menu for managing and opening decks (that can be seen in the calendar) and for assigning members to specific tasks, and
- a sub-menu for internal surveys and polls.

All members have their own manageable profile page with which they can offer personal information such as email address, company, contact details, a profile picture, the role within the project and links to personal websites.

The PYSOLO Nextcloud platform can be adapted in the course of the project and further elements and functions can be added if necessary. Access to Nextcloud is granted by NOVA for up to three months after the end of the project.

Figure 5: PYSOLO Nextcloud platform

2.2.2. Dissemination Notification Procedures

During the project and for a period of one year after the end of the project, any dissemination of own results by one or several parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 17 of the Grant Agreement and its Annex Section Dissemination, subject to the following provisions:

A party shall not include in any dissemination activity another party's results or background without obtaining the owning party's prior written approval, unless they are already published.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other parties **at least 15 calendar days** before the publication. Before the planned publication all project partners will be notified by email through an Advance Notice Text, which includes:

- an attachment of the full (pre)publication or at least the abstract including title, author(s), and partners involved;
- where and when the publication will be submitted to or at which event it will be presented.

Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the coordinator and to the party or parties proposing the dissemination **within 15 calendar days** after receipt of the notice.

Project partners may object if they can show that their protection of results or background would be adversely affected by the publication, their legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed, or their confidential information would become public if the disclosure is permitted. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests on a timely basis (for example by amendment to the planned publication and/or by protecting information before publication) and the objecting party shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if

appropriate measures are taken following the discussion. If no objection is made within the time stated above, the publication is permitted.

The objecting party can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendar days from the time it raises such an objection. After 90 calendar days the publication is permitted, provided that confidential information of the objecting party has been removed from the publication as indicated by the objecting party.

Once partners have completed the publishing requirements, please inform the project consortium about:

- Title
- Author(s)
- Place of publication + issue no. or volume
- Year of publication
- Provide an according link
- Information whether you used green or gold open access
- If green open access, what embargo period was agreed on? (max. 6 months)
- Publication costs (needed for report, eligible for reimbursement)
- ISSN number
- Digital Object identifier, DOI, (if there is one, otherwise a new DOI will be created via Zenodo)

Details on Open Access publication paths are explained in the specific chapter of this document.

2.2.3. Meetings

Project meetings (see **T1.3 Project meetings and internal communication**), as well as WP meetings, will be held regularly to ensure good communication among partners, smooth project development, completion of all tasks and overall success of PYSOLO.

Scheduled project meetings include:

- the online Kick-Off Meeting (6 July 2023),
- the first in-person meeting in Milan, Italy (12 & 13 September 2023),
- the first online consortium meeting (15 February 2024),
- regular partner progress meetings during the project life at least on a six-months basis to coordinate both management and technical issues,
- further consortium meetings in presence once a year and, if possible, coupled to dissemination meetings/workshops.

In addition, several committees within PYSOLO will hold frequent meetings in the course of the project.

These committees include:

- the Steering Committee (SC), chaired by the Project coordinator, which is the ultimate decision-making board of the consortium, involving one representative per partner,
- the Scientific Group, made of WP leaders in charge of the monitoring of the scientific implementation of the project,

- the Industrial Advisory Board (including end-users) will be responsible for supporting the quality review process from an independent and external perspective,
- the Exploitation Committee, chaired by NOVA, which will involve members of the consortium, as well as technical solution developers, industry representatives, market experts, etc.
- the Project Management Office, involving the Project Coordinator, EUCORE staff and all partners' administrative contact persons, which is responsible for overall project management.

In case of upcoming risks or difficulties, more meetings can be scheduled.

2.2.4. Transparency and Accountability

The communication and dissemination strategy of PYSOLO will be guided by the transparency and accountability principles and strategy of The Horizon Europe Programme. C&D will take place during the entire project runtime through a multitude of activities by all partners. These include the website and the social media web portals (Twitter and LinkedIn), press releases as well as publications. Furthermore, all project related events and the collaboration of multipliers and stakeholders within the project will support the idea of transparency and accountability. The project is committed to inform the consortium and the public about progress, financial status and generated results, which among other paths will be realised through continuous reporting and accessible information on the EU CORDIS website of the PYSOLO project, accessible via <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101118270>

2.3. External Communication and Dissemination

2.3.1. Online Activities

Horizon Europe (HEU) Instruments

In order to introduce and spread the generated knowledge and instruments, PYSOLO is going to make use of the pathways provided by the European Commission (EC). This includes the publication of all deliverables, C&D activities and publications on the project EU-CORDIS site, but also technology boosting instruments like the Horizon Results Platform, The Horizon Europe Innovation Radar and the Horizon Magazine. Whenever possible, HEU and the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) will be informed, tagged and actively involved in C&D measures through direct messages or social media related tags, in order to utilise their wide reach and broad network. PYSOLO will also contribute, upon invitation by the CINEA, to common C&D activities to increase the visibility and synergies between HEU supported actions.

Newsletters and Press Releases (PRs)

Newsletters and PRs communicate events, intermediate results, important milestones and extraordinary achievements to all interested stakeholders including key media actors. Throughout the project duration, PYSOLO will publish at least four PRs and will frequently inform about the project via the project partners' company newsletters. The PYSOLO website will also offer a subscription form for a specific project-related newsletter.

The main but not sole actor for the publication of newsletters and press releases will be NOVA. Being one of the leading institutes in the renewable carbon sector, NOVA reaches over 3,500 monthly newsletter subscribers that include all relevant stakeholder and target groups ranging from industrial bodies, policy makers and authorities to the scientific community. NOVA further hosts the daily news platform Renewable Carbon News (<https://renewable-carbon.eu>) that focuses on renewable carbon and reaches more than 300,000 monthly readers. All press releases and news will be published via both paths.

Furthermore, NOVA has access to a press network (Zimpel) with more than 612.000 (inter)national press contacts. In order to maximise project reach and impact, a distribution list with 489 press contacts has been specifically established for PYSOLO.

Project partners are instructed to share links and information on published newsletter articles with the consortium to enable further distribution among the partners' respective networks. All press releases are also made available on the project website.

The start of the PYSOLO project has already been communicated via a press release in English, German, Spanish and Italian, and was distributed by NOVA via Zimpel, a newsletter mailing list, the Renewable Carbon News and on the NOVA website (<https://nova-institute.eu/press/>).

Figure 6: First press release introducing the PYSOLO project in NOVA's Renewable Carbon News

Following NOVA's first press release via Zimpel, several online articles were published on external websites:

Figure 7: Online articles on PYSOLO by external websites following the project's first press release (left: Chemieproduktion-online.de; right: ContextCrew Neue Energie)

Project Video

In order to introduce PYSOLO and communicate its content to the public and interested stakeholder groups in a simplified and visualised form, a project video will be produced which is part of task T5.2. The project video will offer an overview of the project structure and defined project objectives and planned outcomes in an engaging format. Due to the simplified presentation of scientific and technological information it will facilitate communication of project content to a broad audience. The video will be implemented into the project website (<https://pysolo.eu>) and will be available via NOVA's YouTube channel. All project partners will participate in the development of the video and support its promotion and distribution with the consortium's individual networks and media channels after finalisation.

Social Media and NOVA Network

Social Media platforms represent relevant channels for communicating project-related content to the general public and can also be used to disseminate project results to specialised target group. For PYSOLO, mostly LinkedIn and Twitter (now X) will be used for C&D.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a strong network especially for business, policy, science and industry-related posting. It also offers an analytics tool for monitoring and evaluation of content reach and reader engagement.

Most consortium partners possess well-connected LinkedIn profiles with broad professional networks. These include both personal profiles of PYSOLO members and accounts of their affiliated companies and institutions. Project-related content will especially be created by NOVA as the WP lead for C&D and distributed via NOVA's LinkedIn profile (>5,600 followers), the account of NOVA's CEO Michael Carus (>13,400 followers) and the accounts of other NOVA employees involved in PYSOLO. The project partners will be tagged in every post so that it can be liked and shared by the consortium. The C&D team considers the strategy of making use of

already existing LinkedIn accounts to be more efficient than the creation and maintenance of a special PYSOLO LinkedIn community.

Furthermore, LinkedIn features (inter)national interest groups on a wide spectrum of topics. Many project partners have joined such interest groups that allow to target specific content to an interested audience which can serve as mediators of PYSOLO content. These interest groups are for example:

- BioBased Economy
- Biofuel
- Biomass Pyrolysis GVB
- Circular Economy
- Circular economy community – Ellen MacArthur Foundation
- Clean Energy Network – Solar power, Wind, Renewables, Hydropower, Energy efficiency, Sustainability
- Forest Products Society
- Global Energy Profs | Green, Wind, Solar, Oil & Gas
- Pyrolysis World
- Solar Energy Professionals & Consultants
- Solar Power World
- Solar Thermal Power
- Women in Cleantech and Sustainability

All partners are instructed to tag the consortium members, use the hashtag **#PysoloProject** and link to the project website. The hashtag has not been used before and therefore offers great opportunity to be branded and established as a project-specific term. The project partners are further instructed to use related hashtags to increase the distribution range of posts and to target specific stakeholder groups. Possible hashtags include, e.g. **#ConcentratedSolarPower**, **#Pyrolysis**, **#Defossilisation**, **#BioFuel**. All LinkedIn posts should showcase an image to increase awareness and serve as eye-catcher. The addition of alt-texts to images is recommended to make posts barrier-free for visually-impaired persons.

Figure 8: PYSOLO LinkedIn posts by different consortium members

Twitter (now X)

Depending on the further development of this Social Media platform with strongly decreasing numbers of member accounts, the use of Twitter/X will eventually be reconsidered at a later point in time during the runtime of the project. In the meantime, the same strategy as for LinkedIn will apply to the use of Twitter/X. Rather than establishing a new PYSOLO Twitter/X account, it was estimated to have more impact by using already established consortium partner accounts and related hashtags. PYSOLO Tweets will therefore include the project specific hashtag (**#PysoloProject**). This hashtag can be used by all partner Twitter/X accounts as well as all parties that are interested in being connected to PYSOLO. To increase the project reach, related hashtags should be included in Tweets (e.g. **#ConcentratedSolarPower**, **#Pyrolysis**, **#Defossilisation**, **#BioFuel**). By making use of the project's and related hashtags, Twitter allows followers of these hashtags to stay up-to-date on PYSOLO news, developments and results.

All project partners will tag project partners and retweet relevant, project-related Tweets hereby supporting the C&D of project-generated content and news. Also interested stakeholders can directly be tagged. All Tweets should showcase an image to increase awareness and serve as eye-catcher. The addition of alt-texts to images is recommended to make Tweets barrier-free for visually-impaired persons.

Current Twitter figures of PYSOLO partners include @novalInstitut with around 1,900 followers; @RenewableCNews with around 3,850 followers, @mkarus with about 1,180 followers and @polimi with 43,100 followers. Although Twitter/X itself shows lower interaction rates in comparison to other social media platforms, it is proven to significantly increase the recognition of posted content on other channels such as LinkedIn, in Newsletters or website news (Dwivedi et al. 2021).

In order to monitor the success and impact of twitter activities, the partners will use the service "Twitter Analytics" which offers precise information and figures on visitor impressions and reader interaction rates of a specific Tweet.

Figure 9: PYSOLO Tweets by different consortium members

Synergies with Related Projects and Relevant Networks

The consortium will liaise with at least three projects at national, EU and international level that work in the same or similar area in order to get involved in joint activities (e.g. joint events), to exchange on good practises and ideas, and to contribute to mainstreaming and updating of developed results. These projects could include Horizon Europe projects that were funded under the same call (HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-02).

PYSOLO is further going to interact with relevant established networks to further promote results, e. g. ERA-Net Bioenergy by NOVA.

Webinars, Workshops and Stakeholder Events

Different project events and workshop will be organised gathering representatives of key stakeholder and target groups and especially policy-makers. These are:

1. a first mid-term dissemination event in M24 either as a virtual webinar or an in-person workshop organised by POLIMI to present main project findings,
2. a second mid-term dissemination workshop (in-person) in M30 organised by NOVA which will take place either in Brussels or on-site at the PYSOLO pilot plant to increase and mainstream stakeholder engagement,
3. a final dissemination event in M48 in Spain organised by NOVA in order to present and validate all final key project outcomes and to visit the PYSOLO pilot plant,
4. two interactive online workshop/virtual training sessions/webinars for students and researchers will be organised in M12.

The in-person events/workshop can be organised in cooperation with other EU research projects and/or in connection with larger industry events (e.g. in the renewable energy field, or at the Advanced Recycling Conference or the Renewable Materials Conference by NOVA).

Website

The URL for the PYSOLO website was reserved in the first project weeks under <https://pysolo.eu/>. The website is part of task **T5.2 External communication and dissemination** and is hosted and maintained by NOVA in collaboration with the project leader POLIMI. The project consortium supports the lay-outing, decides on the content and the development of the website by providing feedback.

The content of the preliminary website was based on the press release of the project start and consistent of only one page showing the PYSOLO logo and informing on the general project objectives, the used technologies, the coordinator and project partners and contact information. It also displayed the EU logo with funding sentence and disclaimer.

The final website is structured as follows:

- A header with the PYSOLO logo,
- Project main page with a photo slider, an overview on the project objectives, aspired solutions, challenges and technologies,
 - Work package subpage with concise description of related key tasks and messages,
 - Glossary informing about technologies and providing definitions of project-related terms,
- News and media page which provides information and material, such as latest news, downloadable information material (e.g. brochures, roll-up banners, infographic) and press releases,
- Publications and public deliverables page,
- Consortium page with group photo, partner logos and short descriptions,
- Contact page with contact details of the coordinator and the C&D team,
- A footer with EU logo and funding sentence and disclaimer.

Figure 10: PYSOLO website impressions (left: main page, right: consortium page)

The website serves as the main communication and dissemination tool for PYSOLO-related information and results. It will be continuously updated with new information in the form of scientific publications, public deliverables, press releases, scientific schooling material and promotional material. It will further provide access to digital media contributions, e.g., project videos, and will be used for the promotion of PYSOLO-related events such as fairs, conferences, stakeholder workshops and webinars. It will be maintained throughout the project duration and up to five years after the project's completion.

The website performance will be continuously monitored by the analytics tool "Matomo LogFile Analytics", which provides a multitude of useful information about visitor statistics, visit durations and visitor locations. These analyses will serve as a basis for continuous improvement and optimisation of the project website.

All website activities will be accompanied and promoted by additional communication and dissemination activities, e.g. Social Media postings (LinkedIn and Twitter) of news, events, available publications, project videos, newsletters, press releases or publications in professional magazines.

The website is barrier-free to the greatest possible extent. For example: The pictures and colours of the texts and their background colours are chosen to have a high contrast. Each picture receives its own alt-text for visually impaired persons. The icons are designed to be recognisable for red-green colour-blind people. The font of the text is sans-serif to be readable by dyslectic persons.

In order to promote the website, a business card-sized mini-flyer was designed, that can be distributed at events. It shows the PYSOLO-logo and title on the front page and the EU funding sentence and a QR-code leading to the project website on the flipside. It has already been distributed at NOVA's Advanced Recycling Conference in November 2023.

Figure 11: Mini-flyer for promotion of the PYSOLO website

Zoom Backgrounds

Zoom backgrounds serve as eye-catcher during online meetings. They demonstrate affiliation to the PYSOLO project even if the respective participant does not have an active role during the meeting. They also increase recognition and promotion of the project to a targeted audience by referring to the website. NOVA designed two different versions of Zoom backgrounds following the project ID.

Figure 12: Two PYSOLO Zoom backgrounds

2.3.2. Offline and Hybrid Activities and Materials

Brochure or Flyer

A project brochure or flyer can be used for different C&D activities and can be distributed online or in print. In print, it can personally be handed out to interested visitors at fairs and conference, can be taken by visitors that do not wish or do not have time to be involved in long discussions at a booth but are interested in the project, and can serve as reminder after a conference. Online, it can be downloaded from the website by an interested audience and can be distributed via email.

The brochure informing on the PYSOLO project will be established by NOVA with the input from the whole consortium. It will be available in print and online on the News & Media subpage of the PYSOLO website. The brochure will provide background information, inform about objectives and the course of action of the project, and the development of the PYSOLO technologies. It will also contain the infographic and present the general project information (title, acronym, funding statement and disclaimer, the project, EU and partner logos, the runtime and a QR-code leading to the website). The establishment of the brochure is part of T5.2. If necessary, it can be updated in the course of the project.

Event Participation

The presentation of the PYSOLO project at different events like conferences, science and trade fairs and exhibitions and related workshops will enable the exchange of know-how and expertise with a professional target audience. It will further allow concise dissemination of project outcomes, results and chosen methodologies/technologies. Conferences and in-person events will support networking with representatives of relevant communities, such as industry, science and policy. Activities of this sort relate to task **T5.2 External communication and dissemination**.

The consortium will actively promote PYSOLO technologies and research data through presenting and participating at numerous international conferences, trade fairs and exhibitions related to solar power, renewable materials, bio-based fuels, pyrolysis, (wood) biomass, process safety and the related markets. All partners will disseminate PYSOLO results at least at 26 conferences in the related research fields. Events will be selected according to their relevance for the potential project impact and outcomes. In order to promote PYSOLO data, tools, methodologies/technologies and developments to the different stakeholder groups the industrial and academic partners will use exhibition booths at national and international events. Whenever possible, all partners will include PYSOLO in their general communication and dissemination activities on relevant conferences and events.

NOVA organises two conferences relevant for PYSOLO (Advanced Recycling Conference, Renewable Materials Conference) and has many years of experience in organisation and attendance of trade events.

The list with relevant project related industry and academic events included in the CDP will continuously be updated by NOVA and will be provided to all partners:

Table 5: List of upcoming conferences that might be interesting to participate in for PYSOLO members

Date	Conference Name	Venue	Topic	Link
11-12 Jan. 2024	18. International Conference on Solar Power Systems and Grid Connection	Tokyo, Japan	Solar Power	https://waset.org/solar-power-systems-and-grid-connection-conference-in-january-2024-in-tokyo
15-16 Jan. 2024	18. International Conference on Concentrated Solar Power and Technology	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Solar Power	https://waset.org/concentrated-solar-power-and-technology-conference-in-january-2024-in-amsterdam
17-19 Jan. 2024	Intersolar North America	San Diego, CA, USA	Solar Power	https://www.intersolar.us/
22-23 Jan. 2024	Fuels of the Future	Berlin, Germany	Biofuels/gas/char	https://www.fuels-of-the-future.com/en
23-24 Jan. 2024	Solar Quality Summit 2024	Barcelona, Spain	Solar Power	https://www.solarpowereurope.org/events/solar-quality-summit-europe-1

24-25 Jan. 2024	Bio360Expo	Nantes, France	Biofuels/gas/char	https://www.bio360expo.com/lang/en
4-9 Feb. 2024	Renewable Energy: Solar Fuels	Ventura, CA, USA	Solar Power	https://www.grc.org/renewable-energy-solar-fuels-conference/2024/
5-6 Feb. 2024	18. International Conference on Waste-to- Energy Technology and Pyrolysis	Barcelon a, Spain	Pyrolysis	https://waset.org/waste-to-energy-technology-and-pyrolysis-conference-in-february-2024-in-barcelona?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing
6-8 Feb. 2024	Genera (Trade Fair)	Madrid, Spain	Solar Power	https://www.ifema.es/genera
7-8 Feb. 2024	Lignofuels	Helsinki, Finland	Biofuels/gas/char	https://www.wplgroup.com/aci/event/lignocellulosic-fuel-conference-europe/
12-13 Feb. 2024	18. International Conference on Biomass Gasification and Pyrolysis	Istanbul, Turkey	Pyrolysis	https://waset.org/biomass-gasification-and-pyrolysis-conference-in-february-2024-in-istanbul?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing
19-20 Feb. 2024	18. International Conference on Concentrated Solar Power Systems	Rome, Italy	Solar Power	https://waset.org/concentrated-solar-power-systems-conference-in-february-2024-in-rome?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing
28 Feb. - 1 Mar. 2024	K.EY The Energy Transition Expo	Rimini, Italy	Solar Power	https://en.key-expo.com/
29 Feb. - 1 Mar. 2024	Future of Energy	Amsterd am, The Netherla nds	Solar Power	https://www.solarplaza.com/event/future-of-energy/
4-6 Mar. 2024	International Biomass Conference & Expo	Richmon d, VA, USA	Biomass	https://2024-ibce.bbiconferences.com/ema/DisplayPage.aspx?pageId=Home
13-14 Mar. 2024	SolarPower Summit 2024	Brussels, Belgium	Solar Power	https://www.solarpowereurope.org/events/solar-power-summit-2024

19-21 Mar. 2024	Solar Solutions Amsterdam	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Solar Power	https://en.solarsolutions.nl/
26-27 Mar. 2024	Large Scale Solar Europe	Lisbon, Portugal	Solar Power	https://lss.solarenergyevents.com/
12-13 Apr. 2024	18. International Conference on Solar Energy Engineering and Solar Power Systems	Venice, Italy	Solar Power	https://waset.org/solar-energy-engineering-and-solar-power-systems-conference-in-april-2024-in-venice?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing
16-18 Apr. 2024	World Future Energy Summit	Abu Dhabi	Solar Power	https://www.worldfutureenergysummit.com/
17-18 Apr. 2024	PULSE	Madrid, Spain	Solar Power	https://ratedpower.com/pulse/
22-23 Apr. 2024	18. International Conference on Solar Power	London, GB	Solar Power	https://waset.org/solar-power-conference-in-april-2024-in-london?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing
23-25 Apr. 2024	Argus Biomass Conference	London, GB	Biomass Biofuels/gas/char	https://www.argusmedia.com/en/conferences-events-listing/biomass
6-9 May 2024	Cleanpower 2024	Minneapolis, MN, USA	Solar Power	https://cleanpower.org/expo/
19-22 May 2024	IconBM – International Conference on Biomass	Palermo, Italy	Biomass	https://www.aidic.it/iconbm2024/
24-25 May 2024	18. International Conference on Green Energy, Science and Technology	Montreal, Canada	Biofuels/gas/char Solar Power	https://waset.org/green-energy-science-and-technology-conference-in-may-2024-in-montreal
4-6 Jun. 2024	SNEC PV	Shanghai, China	Solar Power	https://pv.snec.org.cn/
10-14 Jun. 2024	Achema	Frankfurt am Main, Germany	Process Industry	https://www.chema.de/en/

11-13 Jun. 2024	FSC Conference - Fuel Science - From Production to Propulsion	Aachen, Germany	Biofuels/gas/char	https://www.tme.rwth-aachen.de/cms/TME/Der-Lehrstuhl/Aktuelle-Veranstaltungen/~pmdn/12-FSC-Konferenz-2024/?lidx=1
11-13 Jun. 2024	Renewable Materials Conference	Siegburg , Germany	Renewables	https://renewable-materials.eu/
18-21 Jun. 2024	Intersolar Europe (Conference an Exhibition)	Munich, Germany	Solar Power	https://www.intersolar.de/video/highlights-of-intersolar-europe-2022?lang=en
24-27 Jun. 2024	European Biomass Conference and Exhibition	Marseilles, France	Biomass Biofuels/gas/char	https://www.eubce.com/
19-20 Jul. 2024	18. International Conference on Concentrated Solar Power Systems, Technologies and Applications	Copenhagen, Denmark	Solar Power	https://waset.org/concentrated-solar-power-systems-technologies-and-applications-conference-in-july-2024-in-copenhagen
22-23 Jul. 2024	18. International Conference on Concentrated Solar Power and Technology	Berlin, Germany	Solar Power	https://waset.org/concentrated-solar-power-and-technology-conference-in-july-2024-in-berlin?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing
27-28 Sep. 2024	18. International Conference on Waste-to- Energy Technology and Pyrolysis	San Francisco, USA	Pyrolysis	https://waset.org/waste-to-energy-technology-and-pyrolysis-conference-in-september-2024-in-san-francisco?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing
18-19 Nov. 2024	18. International Conference on Biomass Gasification and Pyrolysis	London, GB	Pyrolysis	https://waset.org/biomass-gasification-and-pyrolysis-conference-in-november-2024-in-london?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing
tba	3rd World Hydrogen Blue, CCS & Pyrolysis	online	Pyrolysis	https://www.worldhydrogenleaders.com/events/wh-blue-ccs-pyrolysis

tba	PYROLIQ III	tba	Pyrolysis	https://engconf.us/conferences/chemical-engineering/pyroliq-ii-2023-pyrolysis-and-liquefaction-of-biomass-and-wastes/
tba	European Biomass to Power	tba	Solar Power	https://www.wplgroup.com/aci/event/european-biomass-to-power/
tba	Bio-Char IV: Production, Characterization and Applications	tba	Biochar	https://engconf.us/bio-char-iii-production-characterization-and-applications/
tba	10th International Symposium on Energy from Biomass and Waste	Venice, Italy	Biomass Biofuels/gas/char	https://www.showsbee.com/fairs/36311-Venice-Symposium-2022.html
tba	Advanced Recycling Conference	Cologne, Germany	Pyrolysis	https://advanced-recycling.eu/
tba	20th International conferences on renewable Resource and Biorefineries	tba	Biomass Biofuels/gas/char	https://www.biorefine.eu/events/rrb-2023-renewable-resources-and-biorefineries/
tba	International Conference on Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis	tba	Pyrolysis	https://na.eventscloud.com/website/21947/
tba	Solar Power and Chemical Energy Systems Conference (SolarPACES)	tba	Solar Energy Biofuels/gas/char	https://www.solarpaces.org/
tba	The 3rd International Conference on Negative CO2 Emissions	tba	Solar Power	https://www.cvent.com/c/abstracts/81ec99db-d4d6-419a-84b8-76395969b3b1

tba	The 16th International Conference on Applied Energy (ICAE)	tba	Solar Power Pyrolysis Biofuels/gas/char	https://applied-energy.org/icae2024/
tba	58th Annual Loss Prevention Symposium (LPS)	tba	Process Safety	https://www.aiche.org/conferences-events
tba	Fourth European Conference on Plant & Process Safety	tba	Process Safety	https://safetycongress.eu/

Factsheets

Factsheets serve the purpose to educate and inform scholars (including research students) and the general public in a very short, visually appealing and easy to understand way about the project’s technologies, goals and outcomes. For the three factsheets that will be designed for PYSOLO, simple and clear language, a clean design and other visual aids will be applied to ensure the attention of the audience.

Infographic

Infographics present an effective information tool that allows to describe complex processes in a simplified, visualised and structured form. They hereby support awareness and increase engagement and understanding of the tackled topic. Infographics can be used both online (e.g. on the website, in presentations) and in offline communication material.

Posters and Roll-up Banners

A roll-up banner can be used as eye-catcher and attractant for visitors during conferences and at project and trade fair booths. It can also be used during meetings allowing for making photographs in front of the banner for Social Media postings.

Publications

Throughout the project duration, project partners will publish at least 18 scientific and/or technical peer reviewed publications in high-impact scientific journals or in trade magazines.

Results will further be communicated through publications in popular non-scientific magazines (e.g. Bio-based News, BE sustainable magazine) targeting the bio-based industry, the energy and biofuel sector, the scientific community and young researchers as well as policy makers and the broad public.

A first non-scientific article was published in the German e|m|w Magazin:

Schwarzenberger, A., Lorreyte, C., Rincon Duarte, J.P., Roeb, M., García, T., Murillo, R., Veses, A., Miliotti, E. (2023) Biomassepyrolyse – erneuerbare Rohstoffe für die Chemieindustrie. e|m|w Magazin, 6/23.

<https://www.emw-online.com/artikel/238793/biomassepyrolyse-erneuerbare-rohstoffe-f-r-die-chemieindustrie>

Figure 13: Frontpage of the first non-scientific article in the e|m|w Magazin 6/23

3. Standards

Public data and research outputs generated by PYSOLO will be managed as according to Art. 17, Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement (GA) and in line with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). The innovative findings and results of the project will be disseminated to other researchers and interested stakeholders via green or gold Open Access (OA) in peer-reviewed papers. All project related publications will include required Metadata information, follow the OA guidelines of the European Commission and a FAIR science approach and will be made available through a free online repository (Zenodo) and on the project's website.

3.1. Open Access (OA)

3.1.1. Legal Requirements

The beneficiaries must ensure OA (i.e. open, free-of-charge access to the end-user) to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- they disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.
- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND).
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Where the call conditions impose additional obligations regarding the validation of scientific publications, the beneficiaries must provide (digital or physical) access to data or other results needed for validation of the conclusions of scientific publications, to the extent that their legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded (and unless they already provided the (open) access at publication).

Where the call conditions impose additional open science obligations in case of a public emergency, the beneficiaries must (if requested by the granting authority) immediately deposit any research output in a repository and provide OA to it under a CC BY licence, a Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent. As an exception, if the access would be against the beneficiaries' legitimate interests, the beneficiaries must grant non-exclusive licenses — under fair and reasonable conditions — to legal entities that need the research

output to address the public emergency and commit to rapidly and broadly exploit the resulting products and services at fair and reasonable conditions. This provision applies up to four years after the end of the action.

3.1.2. Publication Types

Peer-reviewed publications are those assessed by other qualified scholars and experts. A peer review is typically, though not exclusively, organised and initiated by the journal or publisher to which an article or manuscript is submitted. The dominant type of scientific publication is the journal article.

Besides, all partners are also strongly encouraged to provide open access to **other types of scientific publications**. These include project results such as:

- Monographs
- Cumulative dissertations
- Books and chapters
- Conference proceedings
- Grey literature (non-peer-reviewed publications, e.g. reports, pre-prints).

Besides, also **research data** (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data) can be deposited in an appropriate data repository. Open Research Europe strongly encourages the use of community-recognised and discipline-specific repositories where they are available. If data cannot be shared openly, for example to protect the privacy of research participants, a repository can be chosen which restricts or controls who can access the data and for what purposes. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The chosen data repository should provide a persistent identifier for each dataset that is deposited.

3.1.3. OA Pathways

After depositing publications each partner must ensure open access to those publications via a chosen repository. Beneficiaries can choose one of two main pathways to meet this requirement:

- **Self-archiving/'green' OA:** Beneficiaries can deposit the final peer-reviewed manuscript in a repository of their choice. They must ensure OA to the publication within a maximum of 6 months (12 months for publications in the social sciences and humanities). To provide support concerning compliance with Horizon 2020 embargo periods, the Commission offers a model amendment to publishing agreements which are often signed between authors and publishers. This model is not mandatory but reflects the obligations for the beneficiary under the H2020 and Horizon Europe grant agreements. It can be supplemented by further provisions agreed between the parties, provided they are compatible with the Grant Agreement. The Commission/Agency takes no responsibility for the use of this model.
- **OA publishing/'gold' OA:** Researchers can also publish in open access journals or hybrid journals that both sell subscriptions and offer the option of making individual articles openly accessible. Monographs can also be published either on a purely OA basis or using a hybrid business model. 'Article processing charges' are eligible for reimbursement during the duration of the project (as other costs defined in Article 6.2.D.3 of the Model Grant Agreement). As stated, the article must also

be made accessible through a repository upon publication. Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement. Costs of 'gold' open access publications incurred once the project is completed cannot be refunded from the project's budget.

3.1.4. Free Open Access journals

The scientific landscape covers opportunities for free of charge Open Access publishing venues. An overview of Open Access publishing venues without APCs (Article Processing Costs) can be found here: www.doaj.org.

3.1.5. Zenodo Community

In order to ensure OA to all project related publications and materials (publications, presentations, conference proceedings, flyers, brochures, scientific posters and other scientific schooling material) even after the project has ended, NOVA established a Zenodo Community. Zenodo is a free of charge online repository built and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE in order to ensure pathways to and participation in Open Science as well as FAIR research outputs. All research results and publications are stored safely for future use by the broad society in CERN's Data Centre for as long as CERN exists. All materials published up to this point in the project process will be added to this online group and linked to the project website. The approach simplifies the publication process and ensures that knowledge gained throughout the project remains accessible to the public and interested stakeholders even after the project ends.

Zenodo further allows an easy citation of scientific work by using a so-called Digital Object Identifier. The DOI identifies and links to an authoritative version of the publication. In all cases, the European Commission encourages authors to retain their copyright and grant adequate licenses to publishers. In this context, Creative Commons offers useful licensing solutions. This type of license offers a suitable legal tool for providing open access in its broadest sense.

The PYSOLO Zenodo Community is accessible under the Link <https://zenodo.org/communities/pysolo>. It will remain updated throughout the duration of the project period as well as after the project has ended. Additionally, Zenodo will allow an easy transfer and integration of uploaded publications, data sets, scientific materials and research results to the EC Cordis page of the BioReCer project.

Figure 14: The PYSOLO Zenodo Community

3.2. FAIR Science and Metadata

All project partners must manage the digital research data generated within the action responsibly and in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable). These will secure the ‘findability’, ‘accessibility’, ‘interoperability’ and ‘re-usability’ of data and information and hereby maximise the project’s impact. Partners therefore must deposit and ensure open access to the deposited data to PYSOLO partners and to the European Commission for verification purposes (if required). The generated datasets set as “public” in the **D1.2 Data Management Plan** (due in M12), will be made accessible for the public in the general repository “Zenodo” linked to OpenAIRE.

The Metadata of deposited data and publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following:

- Publication: author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue; datasets: description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo;
- Horizon Europe funding and disclaimer;
- Grant project name and acronym and number;
- Licensing terms;
- Persistent identifiers such as the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) of a publication,
- Authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and their grant.
- Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

If necessary for the realisation of the project, license free access to background and foreground will be provided to all participants of the network. For further research and exploitation rights beyond the project, the consortium declares to provide each of the participants access to results and technologies on reasonable conditions.

Nightly backup and replication into multiple copies in the online system will be performed for the safe storage of data. The long-term preservation strategy will ensure that the tools, as well as the primary qualitative and quantitative data produced throughout the project can be found, understood, accessed, and used for at least ten years after the project completion.

Publishable data will be transferred to the Zenodo online repository, which will ensure sustainable archiving of the final research data. Items deposited in Zenodo will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. Zenodo is hosted by CERN within the framework of the European Commission's OPENAir framework.

More information on data handling and IP processing are provided in deliverable **D1.2 Data Management Plan** (DMP) which includes the guidelines on how to make shared data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR).

3.3. Gender, Equal Opportunity, Diversity and Inclusion

Equality between women, non-binary persons and men in research and development is an essential condition for the optimal execution of Horizon Europe projects. The members of PYSOLO consortium are not influenced by any prejudice against persons from single or intersected diversity dimensions and promote gender equality in agreement with the EU Chart of Fundamental Rights. PYSOLO will aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action (i.e. scientific and technical staff), including the supervisory and managerial level. PYSOLO will also actively take measures to support equal opportunity and participation of women, non-binary persons and men in line with the gender equality plans wherever applicable. All partners but especially women and non-binary persons from the consortium will be encouraged to disseminate generated project results through active participation in conferences, courses, classes and other measures. Furthermore, PYSOLO aims at a balanced representation of women in any stakeholder activity executed throughout the project (if feasible).

Sex and gender will be addressed as a variable during project execution for those tasks in which it may influence the pursued outcome, although the PYSOLO research and innovation purpose is probably not concerned by the gender dimension due to its intrinsic non-gendered nature. Nevertheless, the project will improve public trust and credibility for the acceptance of the novel PYSOLO technology and its green electricity, bio-oil and biochar products, boosting their marketability. Under this framework, sex and gender dimension issues can arise (e.g. acceptance of renewable energies).

Sex and gender will be considered in all promotion/communication measures. This will also apply to aspects like human rights, working conditions or cultural heritage with many different sub-indicators. All created C&D material will display people from different diversity dimensions (e.g. socioeconomic and cultural backgrounds, physical features and gender) to ensure an appropriate representation of the broad society.

In addition, all documents created in PYSOLO will use non-discriminatory and inclusive language. All activities and materials will be published as barrier-free as possible. This includes: i) Graphical material with high contrast and avoidance of colours that cannot be differentiated by red-green colourblind persons, ii) Hashtags that should disentangle the separate compound words with uppercase letters (i.e. CamelCase), e.g., #PysoloProject, in order to make them readable for dyslectic persons, iii) alt-texts for imaging to make it accessible for visually impaired persons, iv) video subtitles for hearing impaired persons, v) barrier-free events. All research results will be disseminated and communicated in a transparent, fair and unbiased way with respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment. This approach will further transfer to all forms of external communication and activities.

3.4. Funding Statement and EU Emblem

According to the Grant Agreement, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate), unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority. The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the EU emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos. For PYSOLO's C&D activities, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority.

More information and guidelines can be found here https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en#how-to-acknowledge-eu-funding

Different versions and languages of the EU logo are available here for various purposes https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/symbols/european-flag_en.

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Figure 15: EU emblem with the European Flag and the Funding statement (in English)

When publishing a peer-reviewed manuscript, we recommend adding the following funding sentence:

“The PYSOLO project receives funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme under grant agreement number 101118270”

In addition, as per **Article 17.3** of the GA, any communication and dissemination activity and all public deliverables related to the action must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

4. Monitoring and Evaluation

In order to allow a seamless monitoring and evaluation of executed communication and dissemination actions and measures, PYSOLO develops suitable instruments and defines related KPIs. The instruments chosen for monitoring are the subject of the presented chapter.

4.1. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

To evaluate the overall performance of executed communication and dissemination activities, suitable KPIs for each C&D activity have been created. They will constantly be monitored, and deviations from this ideal scenario will be intercepted by corrective measures if possible.

Table 6: List of activities and defined KPIs per each stakeholder group

C&D Activities	Target/Stakeholder Group								KPI	Achieved
	Academia	Bioenergy/ Biofuel Sector	Farmers/ Farmers Assoc.	Industry/ Industry comm.	Policy Makers	Regulatory Organisations	Press & Media	General Public		
Conference Participations	X								26	
Factsheets			X					X	3	
Newsletter articles/ PRs	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	5 articles 4 PRs	1 PR (in Engl, Germ, Ital, Span.)
Publications (OA)	X	X		X				X	18	
Publications (non- scientific)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	3	1
Social Media	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	20 posts/a with > 500 impressions	
Video	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	1 with >2,000 views	
Webinars/ Workshops	X	X		X	X	(X)			2 webinars for students/young researchers with >70 participants 2 mid-term workshops and 1 final dissemination event with >50 external participants from at least 7 countries	
Website	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	>10,000 average views per month	

4.2. Tracking of C&D Activities

4.2.1. ECAS Sheet

Throughout the project duration, all C&D activities have to be documented and reported to the European Commission (EC) via the EU Cordis portal of the PYSOLO project. In order to ensure a seamless documentation and monitoring of all partner activities throughout the project duration, NOVA created a Microsoft Excel worksheet, a so-called ECAS sheet. This sheet gathers information on all kinds of possible measures, e.g., conference participations, organisation of workshops, social media activities, press releases and various sorts of publications. It also estimates and monitors the audience numbers reached through these specific activities, divided in various relevant stakeholder groups. The assignment of stakeholder and audience groups is based on the partners' own individual information, surveys or estimations.

The document front tab contains a summarising tracking chart which offers an overview of all C&D activities carried out to this point in time. In a second tab all kinds of C&D activities can be listed. The third tab is destined for listing OA and peer-reviewed publications, as well as published preprints (with DOI). All project partners are required to establish their own documentation of the sheet that will frequently be collected by NOVA (about every six months). All partners' ECAS sheets will be combined in a final master sheet by NOVA which will serve as a basis for activity evaluation based on prior defined KPIs and listed communication goals. It also provides a database for technical reporting and for D5.3 (Dissemination and Communication Package) per each reporting period.

NOVA will be responsible for transferring all information into the EU Cordis portal.

The screenshot displays three overlapping Excel spreadsheet tabs. The top tab shows a summary chart with columns for 'Type of publication', 'Title (article/ chapter)', 'Authors', 'Link', 'Year of publication', 'Open access type', and 'Reference'. The middle tab is a table with columns: 'Activity', 'Name', 'Description', 'Link', 'Date (dd/mm/yyyy)', 'Main Target Audience', 'Outcome', and 'Status'. The bottom tab is titled 'Dissemination & Communication Activities for the Pysolo Project:' and contains a list of activity categories with corresponding counts. The categories include:

- Number of Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the project:
 - Organization of a Conference: 0
 - Organization of a Workshop: 0
 - Press Release: 0
 - Non-Scientific and Non-Peer-Reviewed Publication (regular and preprint): 0
 - Exhibition: 0
 - Flyer: 0
 - Training: 0
 - Social Media: 0
 - Webinar: 0
 - Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV): 0
 - Participation in a Conference: 0
 - Participation in a Workshop: 0
 - Participation in an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop: 0
 - Video/Film: 0
 - Brochure/Event: 0
 - Book Event: 0
 - Trade Fair: 0
 - Participation in Activities Organized jointly with other H2020 Projects: 0
 - Other (Dissemination/Communication activity): 0
 - Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research): 0
 - Industry: 0
 - Civil Society: 0
 - General Public: 0
 - Policy Makers: 0
 - Media: 0
 - Inventors: 0
 - Customers: 0
 - Other: 0
- Number of persons reached, in the context of all dissemination and communication activities:
 - Academics: 0
 - Publication in Conference Proceedings/Workshop: 0
 - Scientific Publications: 0
 - Chapters in Books: 0
 - Theses/Dissertations: 0
 - Other Publications: 0

Figure 16: PYSOLO ECAS sheet

4.2.2. Evaluation of C&D Outcomes

The evaluation of C&D activities will be calculated or estimated by each partner and will be included in the ECAS sheets that will frequently be collected by NOVA. These numbers will be uploaded into the EC portal. The targeted goals per each activity should follow the defined KPIs, and activities should therefore be planned and realised accordingly.

The outcomes of the different activities should be calculated/estimated as according to the following list:

- Events = number of attendees online and/or in person
- Newsletters = your number of regular newsletter subscribers
- Offline materials = number of printed and distributed copies
- Social Media:
 - with Twitter/X analytics = number of impressions per post
 - with LinkedIn statistics = number of impressions per post
- Video = total number of views
- Website = number of average visitors per month

5. Executed and Upcoming Activities

The following C&D activities have already been executed:

- Establishment of a graphical ID (including logo, colour code and templates)
- Set-up of an internal platform for data exchange and internal communication (via Nextcloud)
- Set-up of an ECAS-sheet for the collection of C&D activities by NOVA
- Set-up of a website (<https://pysolo.eu/>)
- Establishment of Zoom backgrounds
- A first PR (in English, German, Italian and Spanish) which was also send out to subscribers of NOVA's renewable carbon newsletter
- A first non-scientific publication
- A mini-flyer for the promotion of the website
- Social media posts by several partners and reposting in different relevant LinkedIn groups

Within the next six months, the following C&D activities are going to be executed:

- Design of a brochure including an infographic of the project
- Design of a roll-up banner following the project's graphical ID
- Contacting of other EU projects in order to become related projects for joint activities
- Organisation of the first webinar/virtual training session for students and researchers in M12
- Continuous updating of the website
- Ongoing social media posting

6. Conclusion

With the set-up of the project's graphical ID (including the logo and templates for reporting) and the DCP, the basis is set for concise and continuous internal communication and external C&D activities during the runtime of PYSOLO and beyond. The strategy set in the DCP will maximise the project reach and will generate impact on a social, economic, scientific but also environmental scale.

This will be achieved through tailor-made instruments and channels addressing the specific target and stakeholder groups. To measure and monitor the success of the selected measures, suitable KPIs have been defined which will be the basis for organisation and execution of all external C&D activities.

The latest measures and activities have focused on introducing and promoting PYSOLO.

7. List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EUCORE	Description 1
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
F2F	Face-to-face
HEU	Horizon Europe
ID	Identity
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
M	Month
MS	Milestone
NIMBY	not in my backyard
NOVA	nova-Institut GmbH
OA	Open Access
PR	Press Release
PU	Public
PYSOLO	PYrolysis of biomass by concentrated SOLar pOwer
R&I	Research and Innovation

RP	Reporting Period
SEN	Sensitive
T	Task
WP	Work Package

8. References

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Schwarzenberger, A., Lorreyte, C., Rincon Duarte, J.P., Roeb, M., García, T., Murillo, R., Veses, A., Miliotti, E. (2023) Biomassepyrolyse – erneuerbare Rohstoffe für die Chemieindustrie. *e|m|w Magazin*, 6/23.

Pysolo Colour Codes and Format Templates

<p>Yellow</p> <p>CMYK 0 20 100 0</p> <p>RGB 254 200 0</p> <p>Hex #FEC800</p>	<p>Brown</p> <p>CMYK 20 65 80 40</p> <p>RGB 140 76 34</p> <p>Hex #8C4C22</p>	<p>Blue</p> <p>CMYK 80 45 0 0</p> <p>RGB 41 119 186</p> <p>Hex #2977BA</p>	<p>Orange</p> <p>CMYK 0 70 100 0</p> <p>RGB 238 99 0</p> <p>Hex #EE6300</p>
			<p>Dark Blue</p> <p>CMYK 80 75 35 60</p> <p>RGB 39 38 60</p> <p>Hex #27263C</p>

Formatierung löschen
EndNote Bibliography
EndNote Bibliography Title
Footer
Py_Header_noNumber
PyBlueBold_10pt
PyContents Header
PyDocument Title
PyGrafic
PyHeader_no_numbering_pagebreak
PylmageCenter
PyReferenceNumber
PyStandard
PyTableHeader

Absatz-Standardschriftart
PyBoldBrown_10pt
1. Überschrift 1, Pysolo_Header
1.1. Überschrift 2, Pysolo_Header 2
1.1.1. Überschrift 3, Pysolo_Header_3
Überschrift 4
Beschriftung, Pylabeling
Verzeichnis 1
Verzeichnis 2
Verzeichnis 3
Abbildungsverzeichnis
Fußzeile
Hyperlink
Kopfzeile, PyHeader